

DEVELOPMENT OF ART AND CREATIVITY IN CHILDREN

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Abstract:

Every invention and creation, no matter in what field, is the outcome of a search for solutions and distinct ideas. Creativity is a *sine qua non* for development and improvement. This view has been a central focus in every field and a considerable volume of research has sought to find out how creativity starts, occurs and develops. Creativity is also a principal element of change and progression. Art can be defined as the manifestation of creativity and imagination. As the lively debate about what is art and what is not art continues, new meanings are assigned to art. Art is, in general, a reality that should exist in everyone's life, whether an adult or a child. Since creativity emerges as the beginning of art in children, children's art (paintings, drawings and other works produced by children) is of key importance. A child's development can be followed in his or her art.

Keywords: child, art, creativity, development, existence

Introduction

George Bernard Shaw writes "*The reasonable man adapts himself to the world; the unreasonable one persists in trying to adapt the world to himself. Therefore all progress depends on the unreasonable man*" (as cited in Evans & DeHaan, 1988: 63). Shaw's famous remark highlights that a creative perspective is required to seek out new ways for the unknown and unresolved; and progress depends on it.

Creativity is a broad concept that contains many definitions and descriptions. It refers to generating, inventing and devising. It is a restless process of change and formation (San, 1985).

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The concept of creativity is involved in every aspect of life. This concept is used in a wide range of areas including science, works of art, advertising, fashion, decoration, industrial products on the market, and so on. This allows human beings to put forward different views on creativity.

Creativity is comprehensively addressed in Ellis Paul's *"The Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking"*. Creativity is an effort to be aware of and come through difficulties, a need to prove what is right or wrong, an attempt to formulate hypotheses about generalizations or proposals, and the sensitivity to disruptions, deficiencies, the lack of information and the environment. And it involves transferring the outcome of all these acts to different people (Sungur, 1997).

In fact, creativity itself gives answers to the questions about creativity. It carries a nonrestrictive and broadening meaning and involves the capacity to develop a different point of view and solve problems accordingly. In short, creativity is an effort to look for and find different ways and to provide different solutions for each question (Becer, 1993).

Human beings try to manifest their existence by adding new meaning to the existing one or by introducing something new. This is a necessity to take part in creation (May, 1994). Each person has a distinct reality of creativity that arises from his or her effort to fix the disconnection between the inner world and the outer world (Tozar, 2002).

This reality actually begins with a person's concerns about and questioning his or her existence and universe in order to learn and understand what is going on. Wondering and questioning seem to be enough for a beginning, but in fact, it is not. It is also important to find answers and give clarifications to questions.

Sociologists, artists, psychologists and many others have tried to describe and interpret creativity. There are a plenty of resources available. As creativity has a broad meaning, a need has arisen to classify it. For example, Eric Fromm classifies creativity in two categories. The first is the creative action that is learned and developed through abilities for visual arts, music, literature, etc. and thus helps to produce a piece of work. The second is the whole of the reactions that are at the core of creativity. These reactions may not appear through a piece of work since they differ among individuals and depend on the specific personality of each individual. Creativity can be developed through the activation of all senses (Gönen et al., 2006).

Social psychologist Irving Taylor addresses human creativity at five levels:

1. The primitive and intuitive expression that is natural and spontaneous, basic and intrinsic, does not need talent, is especially found in children's paintings, and results from the act of playing.
2. The productive creativity that leads a person consciously toward a conclusion.

3. The inventive creativity that refers to exploring and inventing new things using what is available.
4. The innovative creativity that involves isolating from the existing thoughts and the objective content of a concept.
5. The imaginative creativity that is brought about by the existence of a person.

The first level, primitive and intuitive expression, holds a significant place. The creative process in children's works produced in a play setting as an act of the primitive and intuitive creativity is an important factor in a child's artistic development.

However, the utmost importance of the imaginative creativity as the highest creative level is illustrated by examples in art history. Indeed, an artist at the level of imaginative (genius) creativity has a well-developed skill of abstraction and can be a pioneer of a new art style or design.

According to Sigmund Freud, creativity results from the conflict between libido and subconscious. Thus, the basic instincts of a creative person are presented in an acceptable manner. It, however, has no connection with reality (Storr, as cited in Çoban, 1999: 45).

Freud's interpretation of art as the power uncovered for pleasure considers art the idleness of those who have not spiritually developed and do not want to develop (Yavuzer, 1989). However, Freud's idea that artistic creation is an idle thing is not acceptable.

Generally speaking, creativity is a property that everyone has and will have throughout his or her life and a sequence of events that happens in a wide range of areas. It is a manner and attitude.

The concept of creativity is defined from a religious perspective apart from scientific, artistic, and linguistic perspectives. Oriental philosopher Krishnamurti: has a very distinct perspective on creativity. According to him, creativity is revealed by what is unpleasant and annoying. As the resultant discomfort reaches its peaks, the process of creativity starts. Here, Krishnamurti, in fact, tells of a divine phenomenon. God is creativity itself (Krishnamurti, 1988)

J. Englebright Fox and Robert Schirrmacher also define creativity. They (2014) list a number of recognized definitions as follows:

1. Seeing from an unusual point of view,
2. Adding new information to the existing information and keep ahead of the accepted one,
3. Thinking out of the box or stereotypes,
4. Doing something unique and qualified,
5. Combining different and unrelated things to produce something new.

One of the oldest and most comprehensive definitions of creativity is proposed by Stein: Every creative work is a novel beginning. Every innovation needs to be persuasive and acceptable to the relevant society with the help of time. What is meant by 'novelty' is that the creation does not exist before. That is, it depends on all the characteristics of the creator (as cited in (Akt. Runco & Jeager, 2012).

The concept of art has a broad framework such as creativity. To briefly define, art is the recreation and reflection of reality depending on the aesthetic perception of a person. Art is a key part of self-expression, self-renewal, self-unity, emotional healing, or being a human (Wright, 2003).

According to Belinsky, art arises from the aesthetic internalization of everything from the general to the specific. Art is really an effort to create a work of art that allows the perception and internalization of a matter or meaning. Aesthetics is a very special and important issue that includes beauty and its effects (Atalayer, 1994).

Art is the most significant phenomenon in terms of development in all societies. Art helps everyone, including children, to combine and integrate what they learn and know in all social and human sciences. The most important aspect of art is individualization in education (Brewer, 2001).

It is not true to limit art education to visual education. It is a road that contains all the ways of education. Art education is the process of understanding the difference between looking and seeing, learning to see something, becoming aware of something, and creating taste and aesthetic values. The subsequent process of creation results in pleasure (Gürtuna, 2007).

It is the basic tenet of art to look for what is beautiful. And it is the result of dislikes. Thus, people become sensitive. However, art education is centered on understanding rather than searching for the beautiful and accordingly develops learning methods. As a result, individual views of life are distinguished and learning becomes easier. Therefore, art should be provided to children at a young age to let distinct views of life develop (Özünel, 2005).

Art involves a process of self-renewal that expands and grows to renew the whole worlds. Art is the most general expression of creation and image power. The efforts to describe art with new narrow definitions despite its broad sense are obvious in ever-changing thoughts about what art is or what is art. Although art is sometimes defined in a very simple and clear way, there is still a lively debate about how it is defined.

Senses are the origin of information. However, information generated merely by senses is not necessarily always correct. People learn all the properties of the universe in which they live, detach them from their objective content, isolate their thoughts from objects, and then transform them into information. Each person has his or her unique

sensory information. Thus, art is the fact that people develop this abstract background into a concrete outcome through this originality (Atalayer, 1994).

Creation is seen in scientists, literary intellectuals, and especially artists. Creativity considered to be a characteristic of extraordinary people was long perceived as a concept that belongs only to the field of fine arts. Thanks to the changing way of thinking in later years, creativity takes its place as a concept with a wide range of meanings and uses.

Creation requires a certain amount of time. In other words, the process of creation is the most important stage of creativity. According to Aristotle, an artist's inner desire to create is his or her purpose to incorporate into life the outcome of his or her research in the process of creation (Eugene & DeBruhl, 1996). The concept of artistic creation can define a different attitude and path of expression.

For creative action, artists must be aware of the world, which requires special effort.

The first condition in creative action is the occurrence of an encounter. Artists must first meet with what they plan to paint. They may encounter a landscape, object or colors. Then they look at and contemplate what they encounter. They try to manifest it using their creativity and imagination (May, 2005).

Children draw pictures for fun and play. They also convey what they cannot tell through drawing pictures. Children have difficulty in expressing all their feelings as their ability to convey their thoughts is not fully developed until they learn reading and writing. Thus, they unconsciously convey what they want to explain by drawing pictures. At first, their drawings may not make a sense. However, it should be noted that they can carry deep hidden meanings (Çankırılı, 2011).

As a matter of fact, children's paintings were ignored until the late 19th century. It was only in the early 20th century that children were also addressed within the scope of creativity. From this time on, it has been proven that children's drawings have similarities although children are from different nations and cultures (San, 1992).

Every child has creativity regardless of the cultural or national background. It is a strength to be supported and developed. Creativity is a concept that embraces all behaviors (Jalongo, 2003).

Thus, creativity is a phenomenon that must be always kept alive as it plays a critical role in sustaining life, enriches our life experiences, and prepares people to deal with the rapidly expanding knowledge and challenges of the new world. Creativity is a need not only for artists but also for the society. Therefore, creativity is the essential building block of early childhood (Kagan, 2003).

It seems to be wrong to think of creativity at an advanced age. The integration of creativity in all activities of children from early childhood is of crucial importance for children's development. The role of art is, no doubt, essential in the development of

children's creativity. Children should be offered all the factors in the creative process at a very early age.

All creative activities offered in early childhood are important in mental and brain development. There is a considerable volume of research to support this. It is of paramount importance that children should be easily able to engage in drama, music, playing, dancing, storytelling, artistic and cultural activities (Elliott, 2005).

Artistic development theories try to explain what, why, and how children create. These theories have both common and distinct aspects. All artistic development theories seek to explain a child's artistic development. However, each has a different focus. Some theories make this explanation better and more comprehensive than others.

These theories include:

1. Physical= Bodily
2. Spiritual = Emotional
3. Awareness = Perceptual
4. Overall progress = Overall developmental
5. The functioning of intelligence - Progression = Cognitive-developmental (Aral & Duman, 2014). Theories provide a good basis for what is done. Different practices arise from different perspectives.

There are different ways of developing creativity. One should be patient to let children complete their own processes and return to themselves and to let them repeat these processes if needed (DeBord, 1997; Feldhusen & Treffinger, 1980 as cited in Fasko, 2011; Woolf & Belloli, 2005).

For the positive development of creativity, an individual should first avoid the factors that impede his or her creativity. In other words, he or she should first find out what hinders his or her creativity. Coon (1983) listed the factors that inhibit creativity as follows:

1. Emotional barriers
2. Cultural barriers,
3. Learned barriers,
4. Perceptual barriers,
5. Heavy-loaded curriculum barriers.

Artistic activities are the most appropriate way to engage children in the process of creation at a young age. From this perspective, art education must be involved in education and training (San, 1979).

What is the relationship between a child's development and creativity? No matter what form of creativity, a child develops large and small muscle skills using appropriate tools. He or she plays musical instruments, mixes and spreads paintings, draws pictures, and moves her or her body in company with a piece of music or a song.

Creative expression supports physical development. It helps children to communicate with other children in social settings. In some cases, creativity refers to dealing with problems alone. In other cases, it involves social skills including sharing, responding and listening to other perspectives. Creative expression positively contributes to the overall health and qualities of a person (Aral & Duman, 2014).

Conclusion

Creativity can be defined as the ability to think out of the box, to look beyond what everyone knows, and to produce something different. It is also the ability to create a novel and different product, piece of work, or idea using what is already known, experienced or created. People may look at the same thing, object, and fact, but what matters is the difference in perception. Creativity is an important way of reducing and resolving the existing or upcoming problems and finding a way out or different solutions.

All children have creativity and it should always be promoted. Creativity helps to different gain perspectives towards experiences in life and to struggle with obstacles encountered. Thus, it should be the most basic component of education in early ages. Barriers to creative actually begin in a person himself or herself. This process is fixed with the barriers that he or she set up against himself or herself. The process may be maintained due to several reasons including narrow-mindedness, inflexibility, and unwillingness to investigate or question. Once these barriers are removed or reduced, the factors that will lead to development will emerge.

That is, a person must first identify himself or herself. The process of creation will begin as he or she becomes aware of and internalize what is going on. Then, a creative person can be fostered through education.

Creative education enables a child to self-recognize, to know his or her environment, to easily express his or her feelings, to search for solutions to problems, and to build a personality. And this will happen through art and art education. Innovation and uniqueness in art are among the most important factors that promote creativity. Children convey their feelings and thoughts through works of art.

All in all, art must be involved in all domains of life, especially in education, for the development of the self and the society. Thus, it helps to raise individuals who are keen to search and can synthesize and unconventionally generate new knowledge. Instead of memorization-based education system even in early childhood in Turkey, education programs should support the development of creativity as from early childhood. In the education system, the actions of a school are based on the thought of implementing. It is inevitable for schools to adopt this. As a result, this perspective

inhibits creativity. However, children can be treated on a one-to-one basis and helped to uncover and orient themselves. Children should be encouraged to come up with their own answers to questions, especially in early childhood. Children are intellectually distinct individuals who have the capacity to observe and formulate practical theories. Artistic approaches are the most important tool to help children express themselves. There are numerous useful activities that foster creativity such as picture construction, drama, and music to name, but there are just few. Especially the activities in early childhood are of critical importance for creativity. Artistic approaches should be developed and transferred by subject-matter experts starting from early childhood education. There are several examples in the world.

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